

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS AS PART OF THE GREEN DEAL

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ABSTRACT

Emissions from the sectors of agriculture, forestry and land use are responsible for approximately a quarter of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, and if they continue on the current trend they would prevent the achievement of the goals of the Paris Agreement. The European Green Deal defines the EU's future environmental policy to address the challenges of environmental protection in the face of climate change, and one of the essential elements of the Green Deal is a Farm-to-Fork strategy, with an emphasis on establishing an environmentally friendly food sector. Food production worldwide must be transformed in order to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals and to increase the level of resilience of production and processing activities to external factors.

The demand and need for food is growing as the world's population grows, but the amount of arable and pasture land supporting extensive agricultural production is decreasing due to increasingly noticeable climate changes. A part of the future demand for food and nutrition can be met by aquaculture, algae and insects, which, compared to livestock, represent an efficient way of producing protein with relatively low environmental costs. This paper presents some important advantages and disadvantages of the mentioned food systems, as well as additional efforts that must be made in order to achieve the best possible sustainability and acceptability of these systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change impacts all food system processes, reducing their capacity to ensure food safety and nutrition both now and in the future. In addition, emissions from the sectors of agriculture, forestry and land use are responsible for approximately a quarter of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. If they continue on the current trend they would prevent the achievement of the goals of the Paris Agreement. Therefore, the challenge of feeding a growing population sustainably, goes beyond a simplified approach to producing more food, and the management of food systems should be closely linked to climate management. The transformations needed to support sustainable food systems, in current and predicted climatic conditions, require different governance mechanisms and a better understanding of how climate policies affect food security and nutrition security and the sustainability of food systems (Hidalgo et al. 2021). This paper will present some of the ways of sustainable food systems, which in the near future will gain more importance, and humanity will inevitably have to accept them as a mechanism of adaptation to the negative consequences of climate change.

2. METHODS

The literature was searched in academic databases: PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar. The literature used in the work covers the period from 2015 to 2024 and includes works in English, Croatian, Serbian, and Bosnian. Most sources refer to Europe and the Western Balkans, while international works are included for a broader context. Mainly, peer-reviewed scientific papers were used, ensuring the reliability of the data, with a smaller number of expert sources (expert book and official EU data). The literature was analyzed qualitatively using an inductive approach, through thematic categorization: traditional and sustainable aquaculture, algae as a protein source, and insects in human nutrition. Publications were reviewed and cross-referenced to identify similarities and differences in existing research. This enabled the synthesis of data with a view to defining trends and future research guidelines.

3. INTERNATIONAL STRATEGIC RESPONSE TO CLIMATE CHANGES

By signing the *Paris Climate Accords* on climate change in 2015 at the 21st United Nations Conference an agreement was reached to achieve the main goal; limiting the global temperature increase below 2°C, and ideally below 1.5°C, compared to the pre-industrial

period. The accompanying goals are to increase the ability to adapt to the consequences of climate change while ensuring food supply and developing "green" technologies. The *European Green Deal* is a new strategy of the European Union (EU), adopted in 2019 by the European Commission, as a response to increasing global challenges and threats to the environment due to intensified climate change. One of the essential elements of the *Green Deal* is the "*Farm-to-Fork*" strategy, with an emphasis on establishing an environmentally friendly food sector (Vasilkov et al. 2021).

The concept of food systems as complex socio-economic ecological systems has gained importance as an effective point for achieving these goals; reducing poverty and malnutrition and contributing to climate change adaptation and mitigation. Climate change is considered one of the most significant threats to modern food systems. The effects of climate change are expected to affect all processes and functions of food systems, hindering their potential to achieve food safety results in the future (Hidalgo et al. 2021). The world food production must be transformed in order to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals, as well increase the level of resilience of production and processing activities to external factors. The current world population is projected to reach over 9.6 billion by 2050, which will require an increase total food production by about 70 to 100% compared to current production, which is ultimately a tall order. The demand and need for food is growing as the world's population grows. The amount of arable and pasture land supporting extensive agricultural production is decreasing due to increasingly noticeable climate changes. Climate change is a key limiting factor contributing to the reduction of food production. The most widespread abiotic stresses in the world are: extreme temperatures, drought, salinity, floods, nutrient deficiencies and acidic conditions. Globally, the area of agricultural land is about 5 billion hectares, which is 38% of the Earth's land surface. Therefore, alternative and sustainable sources of protein and other nutrients must be researched and developed (Ijaola et al. 2024).

4. SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS

4.1. Sustainable aquaculture

Aquaculture is the industry of growing marine and freshwater organisms under controlled environmental conditions; represents the biomanipulation of the life cycle of cultivated organisms and environmental conditions, including growth and reproduction control and elimination of causes of natural mortality. The aquaculture sector will grow in its production and, according to projections, by 2030 will account for 62% of the total share of global human

nutrition by marine products (FAO, 1988 and FAO, 2016; Gulin, 2017). Part of the future demand for food and nutrition can be met by marine products. Compared to livestock production, aquaculture is an efficient way of producing protein with relatively low environmental costs. This set out international plans to increase aquaculture. Thus, in 2021, the European Commission published new strategic guidelines (*COM(2021)0236*) for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture, in a way that will contribute to the *European Green Deal* and economic recovery after the COVID-19 pandemic. These guidelines also contribute to a "*Farm-to-Fork*" strategy, initiating a faster transition to a sustainable EU food system, while recognizing the potential of sustainable aquaculture in providing food and feed with a low carbon footprint (Gerhard Brauer 2023).

Although there was a four-fold increase in global aquaculture production between 1990 and 2017, total EU production from around 1.2 million tonnes has not changed for a long time despite the Commission trying to improve the EU's production potential by publishing various strategic documents and guidelines (Gerhard Brauer 2023). The challenge for achieving strategic goals for the improvement of aquaculture production is compounded by the fact that ecological, socio-economic, financial and energy sustainable development needs to be integrated in parallel. Traditional breeding technologies are increasingly considered "polluting" and "unsustainable". The fish production process continuously generates solid and liquid waste, as well as carbon dioxide. Approximately 25% of the feed used for aquaculture farming is excreted as solid waste, while liquid waste includes ammonia, nitrites, nitrates, phosphates and other dissolved substances in the growing water. Limited amounts of water, negative impact on the environment and water quality, land price and other challenges, encourage growers and researchers to develop and apply new, more environmentally and economically acceptable breeding technologies that will meet the growing needs for food, but also the trend of healthy eating.

Aquaculture has the potential to increase the global food supply, as well a huge potential to address malnutrition and nutrition-related diseases. Therefore, a segment of the quality of cultivation itself is also important in order to obtain a high-value product, so the choice of the type of feed affects the nutrients available from aquaculture. Fish in the human diet is very beneficial from a health perspective. It provides high-value proteins and various necessary micronutrients: vitamins (A, B and D), minerals (calcium, iodine, zinc, selenium, iron) and polyunsaturated n-3 fatty acids, such as which are docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) (Starčević et al. 2022). With the growth of the population and

increased consumer awareness of the health benefits of using fish in human nutrition, an increase in aquaculture is also expected. The contribution of aquaculture expansion in improving nutrition and increasing the global food supply is limited by the ecological sustainability of aquaculture (Fiorella et al. 2021).

4.1.1. Recirculating aquaculture

One of the alternatives to traditional breeding is recirculation aquaculture. It can be located in both urban and rural areas. The main characteristic of recirculation aquaculture systems is the purification and reuse of water from the the breeding areas. That significantly reduces the need for water changes, and an additional benefit is that they require significantly less space than traditional breeding methods. These systems integrate various individual processes for water purification, and processes for controlling and maintaining the desired water quality during an intensive production regimen. Controlled conditions enable the achievement of optimal breeding conditions adapted to the specific species being cultivated, and thus it is possible to shorten the production cycle in relation to open uncontrolled systems. Better food conversion is also achieved, which means that less waste generated by food goes into the environment, thus creating small amounts of concentrated wastewater that can be processed relatively cheaply (Gavrilović and Jug-Dujaković, 2019).

4.1.2. Biofloc technology in aquaculture

Biofloc technology is considered an effective alternative system in aquaculture by which nutrients are recycled. Biofloc technology is based on the growth of microorganisms in an aqueous medium in order to improve water quality and treat waste products with minimal water exchange and an additional free source of protein for cultivated species.

For sustainable aquaculture, microorganisms rank high: they serve as a source of food for cultivated organisms and for the removal of waste generated in this activity. The sustainable approach of this system is based on the growth of microorganisms in culture medium, with minimal or zero water changes. Biofloc microorganisms have two main roles; maintaining water quality, through the uptake and conversion of nitrogen compounds into microbial protein and as an additional food source for cultivated species, increasing the profitability of the cultivated culture. Microbiological control leads to efficient decomposition of waste materials, efficient nitrification, and facilitates the control and recycling of nitrogen. Biofloc systems are most effective when applied to species of organisms that are able to directly

consume flocculating particles. It is also important that the systems are suitable for species that can tolerate high concentrations of solids in the water and poorer water quality. Some species of prawns and tilapia have physiological adaptations to consume bioflocculating particles and digest microbiological protein. Almost all bioflok systems are used mainly for the breeding of prawns (*Penaeus monodon*, *Penaeus sp.*), Nile tilapia (*Nile tilapia*) or carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idell*) (Gulin, 2017).

4.2. Cyanobacteria and microalgae in human nutrition

Cyanobacteria and microalgae contain significant amounts of protein and lipids, which are highly digestible and nutritionally well balanced (Table1). Spirulina is a biomass of cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) used for the production of food supplements or as a whole food. Spirulina actually includes three species: *Arthrospira platensis*, *A. fusiformis*, and *A. maxima*. *Chlorella vulgaris* is a type of green microalgae from the phylum *Chlorophyta*, which is also used as a dietary supplement, and to improve the nutritional quality of cereal-based products, dairy products and others. Traditionally, *Spirulina* was collected from the wild and consumed as a protein-rich whole food in numerous cultures outside Europe and North America. Today, *Spirulina* and *Chlorella* species are commercially cultivated varieties and are integrated into a number of products: salad dressings, beverages and pastries, and are also sold as protein supplements. Proteins in algae contain all the essential amino acids essential for human consumption. In addition, biomass microalgae and cyanobacteria is extremely rich in numerous bioactive components, which further contribute to the preservation and improvement of human health (Ahmed et al. 2024).

Table 1: Nutritional composition of algae; *Spirulina* and *Chlorella vulgaris* (Ahmed et al. 2024)

Nutrient content in 100g	<i>Arthrospira</i>	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>
Fats	2,2 g	-
Proteins	63 g	60,1 g
Carbohydrates	22 g	40,1 g
Iron	58 mg	240,1 mg
Calcium	1 mg	33,1 mg
Zinc	3 mg	~1,5 mg
Potassium	1,4 mg	-
Magnesium	400 mg	~274 mg

It is important to note that the above two examples are only a small part of the total number of different types and forms of application of marine and freshwater algae in human nutrition. Algae are relatively new to the United States food market, but several types of algae have already received GRAS status from the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), among them: *A. platensis*, *A. protothecoides*, *C. vulgaris*, *Dunaliella bardawil* and others. This designation is assigned by the FDA to substances considered safe for human consumption.

Work should be done to increase the social acceptability of algae as a possible future source of nutrients, primarily because algae are characterized as a reliable and safe source of food. Agricultural activity needs approximately 75% of the total global fresh water, while animal protein requires 100 times more water than if the same amount of protein had been produced from plant sources. The "green alternative" is the commercial cultivation of algae, as most microalgae are photoautotrophs, relying on carbon dioxide as a carbon source and light as a source of energy (Ijaola et al. 2024). However, due to the high water content of the microalgae biomass, water must be removed during processing, which requires high costs and energy. The small cell size of microalgae (2-200 µm) and their growth in very diluted cultures (mass concentration <1 g/L) are key reasons for the high process costs. Also, another challenge is the need to develop improved methods of extracting proteins from seaweed, and with the aim of increasing their bioavailability, because they are poorly digestible in their unprocessed form (Ijaola et al.2024).

4.3. Insects in human nutrition

Insects are part of the common diet of many communities: they are consumed in Africa, South America, Oceania and Asia. In the underdeveloped and less developed countries of Central Africa, insects sometimes make up to 50% of the total protein in human consumption and have a significant market value. Currently, there are more than 2000 species of arthropods from the ranks *Coleoptera* (beetles) with 31 %, *Lepidoptera* (caterpillars) with 17 %, *Hymenoptera* (wasps, bees and ants), *Orthoptera* (crickets and grasshoppers) with 14 %, *Hemiptera* (hemiptera) with 11%, *Isoptera* (termites) with 3 %, *Odonata* (dragonflies), *Diptera* (flies) and others with 9 % (Rakić et al. 2022). The number of people who regularly consume insects is estimated at at least 2 billion (Čaklović et al. 2021). Insects are a source of vitamins, minerals and proteins of animal origin. They require significantly less food to obtain mass and have a lower emission of greenhouse gases compared to the usual farm breeding of animals: pigs or cattle. For example, a house cricket (*Acheta domesticus*) needs 1.

7 kg of dry food for 1 kg for obtain mass, compared to 2 kg for poultry, 3.8 kg for pigs or 7 kg for cattle (Rakić et al. 2022). Compared to other food sources, the advantage of breeding insects as a source of food and feed is that they require less space and water, have a short life cycle and better food conversion. They have significant benefits for the environment, economy and food availability (Starčević et al. 2022).

Under the *Regulation (EU) 2015/2283* on novel foods, insects and products derived from insects are considered novel foods and are subject to an approval process, and whole edible insects and insect-derived ingredients can be lawfully placed on the market. Thus, by *Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/5* authorising the placing on the market of *Acheta domesticus* (house cricket) partially defatted powder as a novel food and amending *Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470*, the placing of the said product on the market was approved for the company "Cricket One" for five years. This company, which is engaged in the production and distribution of insect-based food, has submitted a request that the partially defatted *Acheta domesticus* powder be approved for use in: bread and pastries from several types of cereals, dry premixes for bakery products, crackers, grain bars, biscuits, sauces, soups, processed potato products, dishes based on legumes and vegetables, pasta-based dishes, Whey powder, meat analogues and some other foods and products (Rakić et al. 2022).

One of the biggest obstacles to the use of insects in the diet of humans and animals is food safety. Eating insects carries the risk of chemical, physical and biological hazards and the occurrence of allergies. Cases of histamine poisoning have been recorded after eating fried insects that have a higher histidine content. These health risks when eating insects can be controlled by introducing a good manufacturing practice and hygiene practices (Starčević et al. 2022). Thus, Thailand was the first to describe Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) for breeding crickets. It is necessary to create standard operating procedures and Hazard analysis and critical control points systems (HACCP systems) for raw insects to ensure safe handling, processing and distribution to end consumers (Čaklovica et al. 2021). Countries where insect consumption is commonplace already have well-established breeding and production processes. In 2022, the International Platform of Insects for Food and Feed (IPIFF), as the EU's umbrella organization for the insect production sector, issued the document "Guide to best practices for hygienic and quality insect production". The document describes procedures in the primary production and processing of insects and recommendations for quality and hygiene control, including recommendations for the implementation of the HACCP system in this food sector (Čaklovica et al. 2021).

Figure 1. Realistic representation of insects as food: a) *Acheta domesticus* powder; b) *Alphitobius diaperinus*; c) *Tenebrio Molitor*; d) *Locusta migratoria*

Before the placing on the market of the European Union of any insects is approved, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) provides a scientific opinion on its safety for consumption. Thus, on the EU market, in addition to the *Acheta domesticus* (house cricket) partially defatted powder as a novel food in 2023 (Image 1-a), the European Commission approved the introduction of frozen, dried and powdery forms of *Alphitobius diaperinus* larvae (Image 1-b), better known as the small mealworm, which

EFSA has determined are safe. In the list of insect foods approved by the EU, in addition, there is also the mealworm *Tenebrio Molitor* (Image 1-c) and the *Locusta migratoria* (Image 1-d) have been included since earlier (Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/188).

5. CONCLUSION

World food production must be transformed to achieve the sustainable development goals, and it is also necessary to increase the resilience of existing food production systems to the negative implications of climate change. Food needs increase as the world population grows, while the amount of arable and pasture land for extensive agricultural production is decreasing. Therefore, alternative and sustainable food sources, such as sustainable aquaculture, microalgae cultivation, or insect use in human consumption must be researched and developed, and the public should be educated about the necessity of changes in traditional eating habits and increase the acceptability of these alternative sources of nutrients.

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